

Investigation of High Sensitivity Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors for -0.5...+0.5 kPa

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Abstract. The investigation of the pressure sensor chip's design developed for operation in ultralow differential pressure ranges has been conducted. The optimum geometry of a membrane has been defined using available technological resources. The pressure sensor chip with an area of 6.15x6.15 mm has an average sensitivity S of 34.5 mV/kPa/V at nonlinearity $2K_{NL} = 0.81$ %FS and thermal hysteresis up to 0.6 %FS was created. Owing to the chip connection with stop elements, the burst pressure reaches 450 kPa.

Index Terms—piezoresistive pressure sensor, high sensitivity, temperature error, high mechanical strength, technology upgrading.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important directions of MEMS pressure sensors development is realization of silicon sensing elements able to work in ultralow pressure ranges of 0.1 to 1.0 kPa. Such pressure sensors may find application in many large-scale production fields (medicine, automotive industry, HVAC) and highly specialized scientific developments (seismology, biophysics, robotics) [1]. The opposite side of the task of achieving high piezosensitivity has been and remains an intent to reduce dimensions of a chip and, as a consequence, the package size of MEMS pressure sensors [2,3]. We can minimize the area of a chip by reducing sensitivity, while maintaining the principle of its mechanical design [4]. There are alternative methods for enhancing piezosensitivity or reducing chip dimensions that are associated with the application of a novel electric circuit PDA [5-8] using BJT. The development of such pressure sensors is still at the beginning of the road, but they have already demonstrated an obvious advantage over those with a classical Wheatstone bridge.

Simulated and experimental data on the proposed type of an ultrahigh sensitivity chip of a pressure sensor with a piezoresistive bridge circuit will be presented in the course of the work. In comparison with known analogs, the used chip structure has both strengths and weaknesses [9-13], but the criticality of its parametric values of output characteristics is heavily dependent on the application area of the sensing element.

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II. MODELING

A mathematical model of a pressure sensor chip operating in a range of 0.5 to 0.5 kPa is based on analytical and computer-aided calculation for trade-off relationship between sensitivity (required: $S > 30.0$ mV/kPa/V) and a nonlinearity error (required: $2K_{NL} < 1.5$ %FS). The mechanical part of the sensing element includes a membrane with three separate and two bonded with the chip frame concentrators of mechanical stresses (MS), or rigid islands (RIs), where the thickness of RIs is equal to the initial thickness of a wafer. The selected structure of a membrane with RIs allows concentrating high MS at small values of deflection, which reduces a nonlinearity error [4, 14]. The geometrical shape of the membrane depends on the method of anisotropic wet etching that requires the expansion of the chip area due to silicon etching at an angle of 54.7°. For these types of ultrahigh sensitivity pressure sensor chips reactive ion etching (RIE) is frequently used, which significantly saves the area of a chip [15-20]. Figure 1 shows the geometrical parameters of the selected structure of a chip: L – length of a chip side, W – thickness of the membrane thinned part, H – chip thickness, A – area of the membrane thinned part, D – width of a gap between RIs, Z – length of a RI edge, Y – width of the chip frame, G – width of the membrane etch taper projection, Q_1 – distance between middle piezoresistors (PRs), Q_2 – distance between end PRs. PRs of p-type, covering an area of 20x400 μm , are made on a silicon substrate of n-type ($N_C = 9 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm^{-3}) with a crystallographic plane (100) along the crystallographic direction [110] and have the following parameters: surface concentration $N_{Sp} = 5.5 \cdot 10^{18}$ cm^{-3} , surface resistance $R_{Sp} = 200$ Ohm/cm^2 , depth of a p-n junction $x_{jp} = 2.5$ μm . The main piezoresistive coefficient is $\pi_{44} = 1.26 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$ at room temperature [21, 22]. The calculation of a change in PR rating and, consequently, output sensitivity and nonlinearity is performed using the theory of piezoresistive effect from the following formulas:

$$R_i(\Delta P) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \pi_{44} \cdot \sigma(\Delta P) \right) \cdot R_{i0}, \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta V_{out}(\Delta P) = \frac{(R_1(\Delta P)) \cdot (R_3(\Delta P)) - (R_2(\Delta P)) \cdot (R_4(\Delta P))}{(R_1(\Delta P) + R_2(\Delta P)) \cdot (R_3(\Delta P) + R_4(\Delta P))} V_{in}, \quad (2)$$

$$S = \frac{\Delta V_{out}(\Delta P)}{V_{in} \cdot \Delta P}, \quad (3)$$

$$2K_{NL_j}(\Delta P) = \frac{\Delta V_{out}(\Delta P) - \frac{\Delta V_{out}(0,5 \text{ kPa}) - V_0}{0,5 \text{ kPa}} \cdot \Delta P}{\Delta V_{out}(0,5 \text{ kPa})} \cdot 100\%. \quad (4)$$

where ΔP – applied pressure rating, $R_i(\Delta P)$ and R_{i0} – PR rating ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) when ΔP is applied/ not applied, respectively; π_{44} – main piezoresistive coefficient for PR; $\sigma(\Delta P)$ – MS rat-

ing at ΔP ; $\Delta V_{\text{out}}(\Delta P)$ – output signal of a bridge circuit at ΔP ; V_{in} – bridge circuit supply voltage (5 V); S – sensitivity; $2K_{\text{NL}}$ – output signal nonlinearity error; V_0 – output signal at $\Delta P = 0.0$ kPa; $\Delta V_{\text{out}}(0.5 \text{ kPa})$ – output signal at $\Delta P = 0.5$ kPa. Table I provides geometrical parameters of the structure defined in the process of their variation. Figure 2 shows maps of mechanical stresses and the membrane deflection at $\Delta P = 0.5$ kPa. Figure 3 shows the dependence of sensitivity and nonlinearity on the applied pressure for three thicknesses of the membrane (membrane geometry parameter with the highest dependence). Theoretical values of the output characteristics for the optimum thickness of the membrane ($W = 8 \mu\text{m}$) are $S_{\text{model}} = 34.0 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$ and $2K_{\text{NL,model}} = 0.68 \text{ \%FS}$.

The analysis of possible deformation/deflection of the membrane resulted in determination of the required distances for free movement of the sensing element mechanical structure up to the stops (elements of a silicon assembly), needed to raise, in the operating pressure range, the threshold of burst pressure from both sides of the chip (required: $P_{\text{burst}} > 300$ kPa) [23, 24]. The deflection of the membrane at the rated voltage is $\Delta h_{0,5} = 2.7 \mu\text{m}$. The bottom stop is made as an intermediate element between the chip and the base; it is bonded across the area of the chip frame and has via holes to apply pressure from the base. The top stop has a shape of a regular parallelepiped and is bonded from both sides of the chip, where there are no metallic pads; it also has unbonded regions to apply pressure from the topside of the chip (Figure 4). The gap $h_{\text{touch model}} = 5 \dots 23 \mu\text{m}$ between the chip membrane and the bottom and top stops is ensured by the thickness of a low-temperature bonding glass. The gap may vary to let the membrane move freely in the range of the rated pressure and have a margin up to the point close to destruction [25, 26]. That means that touching should occur at $P_{\text{touch model}} = 1.0 \dots 4.5$ kPa. If the applied pressure exceeds the rated values, the chip membrane (before the moment it breaks) touches the stop and the area with a surface-to-surface contact is reallocated, which stops MS growth.

III. TECHNOLOGY

The main process steps of fabrication of pressure sensor ultrahigh sensitivity chips (Figure 5 and Table II) include:

1. Wafer thermal oxidation;
2. Sequence of micro cycles consisting of photolithography and follow-up doping of impurity of;
 - a. Boron for high-alloy conducting areas of resistors (p^+ -type);
 - b. Boron for low-alloy areas of resistors (p^- -type);
 - c. Phosphorus for a substrate contact (n^+ -type).
3. Si_3N_4 (PECVD) deposition as protection at membrane wet etching;
4. Membrane photolithography on the backside of a wafer (RIE);
5. Anisotropic wet etching of a membrane in 30% solution of potassium hydroxide at a temperature of 85°C ;
6. Anisotropic wet etching in $\text{HF}:\text{HNO}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ solution (2:9:4);
7. Si_3N_4 removal;

8. Photolithography of contact windows;
9. Sputtering of Al-Si (1.5 %) $W_{\text{Al-Si}} = 0,8 \mu\text{m}$;
10. Photolithography on metal surface;
11. Wafer dicing.

Technological processes of formation chip's top side guaranteed a spread in surface resistance R_S and, consequently, resistor rating ($R_{\text{bridge}} = 4.5 \text{ k}\Omega$) within 7% error and the presence of leakage current I_{leak} on p-n junctions of no more than $0.5 \mu\text{A}$ at room temperature at a reverse bias $U_{\text{sample}} = 70$ V. At anisotropic wet etching without self-hardening a spread in the membrane thickness was $\Delta W = \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ over 5 plates 100 mm in diameter. Besides large deviations of the membrane thickness from the required rated value $W = 8 \mu\text{m}$, we also observe asymmetry in the layout of RI edges due to a possible error of alignment at photolithography relative to a primary flat of the wafer and the use of silicon wafers with significantly misorientation crystallographic plane and primary flat (Figure 6a) [27, 28]. This deficiency substantially increases a nonlinearity error as the resistor body (p^- -type) asymmetrically protrudes beyond the length of a RI edge. The further analysis of the obtained assemblies of pressure sensor chips, presented in the section below, showed that there was a difference in the rated values of sensitivity and nonlinearity, when applying pressure from the chip topside and backside, that was quite noticeable at $W < 7 \mu\text{m}$. Residual MS (compressive stresses) in chip structures are caused by the presence on the thinned part of the membrane of a step structure of SiO_2 ($W_{\text{SiO}_2} = 0.2 \dots 0.6 \mu\text{m}$) resulted from diffusion and oxidation processes for different types of doped regions. The elimination of the deficiencies detected for these types of ultrahigh sensitivity chips [29-38] will allow in the future both to increase the percent yield and improve output characteristics within the stated requirements. For the purpose of testing, ultrahigh sensitivity chips of pressure sensors were first combined in a silicon assembly, comprising top and bottom stops and a base with low-temperature bonding glass between them (Figure 4). Connection with the selected geometry makes it possible not only to increase burst pressure of the sensor but also to reduce thermo-mechanical effect of the package [39-41]. The silicon assembly is connected to the package using silicon glue, the chip is wire to the package pins with the help of an aluminum wire (Figure 6b).

IV. OUTPUT CHARACTERISTICS

Prior to testing, all samples of pressure sensors are subjected to thermo- and barocycling in order to remove residual MS from chip bonding. The studies were carried out at the circuit supply voltage V_{in} of 5.0 V for differential pressure in a range of -0.5 to $+0.5$ kPa, with the element topside upwards. The primary parameters for ultrahigh sensitivity chips are sensitivity and nonlinearity that are to be measured at voltage supply from either side because of a certain asymmetry of the characteristics. The samples were divided in 3 groups with regard to the membrane thickness W : No.1 – $5 \dots 8 \mu\text{m}$, No.2 – $8 \dots 9 \mu\text{m}$, No.3 – $9 \dots 11 \mu\text{m}$. Besides differences in the membrane thickness, there are spreads in the width of a gap between RIs

$\Delta D = \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ and the length of a RI edge $\Delta Z = \pm 60 \mu\text{m}$ in each group of the samples.

The study of group No.3 is not relevant because of a low sensitivity $S < 30 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$. Group No.1 with the required values of sensitivity showed that the application of these samples also lost its relevance due to a high nonlinearity error $2K_{NL} > 1.5 \%FS$. Group No.1 was divided into two subgroups based on the sensitivity rated values (No.1.1 – $S \approx 40...60 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$ and No.1.2 – $S \approx 60...90 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$) in order to determine in further studies how greatly, relative to group No.2, an increase of sensitivity affects: 1) nonlinearity for this range, 2) zero signal $\Delta V_0(\sigma_r)$ due to residual MS from a SiO_2 layer. Figure 7 shows the output signal dependence on the applied pressure $\Delta V_{out}(\Delta P)$ for 10 average statistical samples in three types of groups. Table III contains the main output parameters; $\Delta V_0(\sigma_r)$ is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta V_0(\sigma_r) = \left(\frac{\Delta V_{out}(-0,1 \text{ kPa}) - \Delta V_{out}(+0,1 \text{ kPa})}{2} \right) - V_0, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta V_{out}(-0.1 \text{ kPa})$ – output signal at $\Delta P = 0.1 \text{ kPa}$ applied from the topside, $\Delta V_{out}(+0.1 \text{ kPa})$ – output signal at $\Delta P = 0.1 \text{ kPa}$ applied from the backside. Based on the analysis of $\Delta V_0(\sigma_r)$, it may be concluded that residual MSs from SiO_2 bend the thinned part of the membrane towards the topside of the chip, or upwards (Figure 4), which is more evident on subgroup No.1.2. In order to exclude the effect of MSs, arising from bonding the chip with the top stop by low-temperature glass, similar samples of subgroup No.1.2 were combined in an assembly without a top stop and demonstrated the identical bias effect of an output signal $\Delta V_0(\sigma_r)$. The observed effect that also manifests itself at a higher level of sensitivity, when pressure is applied from the topside, is kind of a “flap” of a thin stressed wafer. For elimination of the deficiency the process should be further modified to achieve the final trade-off relationship between MSs of different signs from SiO_2 and Si_3N_4 films [42-45]. Additional application of wet stop-etching and an increase in the length of a RI edge would make it possible not only to considerably reduce a spread in sensitivity, but to minimize the existing nonlinearity errors as well.

Table IV contains characteristics of group No.2 samples (62 samples) with an optimum membrane thickness W of 8 to 9 μm . The calculation of parameters as relative values associated with temperature characteristics, time stability and impact of overload pressure is carried out when pressure is applied from the membrane. Temperature parameters are measured in two separate temperature subranges: negative subrange from $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, positive subrange from $+20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Testing of mechanical strength is performed at an overload pressure P_{proof} of 30 kPa (pressure is applied from both sides of the chip). Time stability of an output signal was monitored within the first 9 hours after supplying power to the chip electric circuits. The effect of RI inertial mass at turning the chip by 180° was considered, which indirectly describes sensitivity of sensing elements, e.g., an accelerometer. With the analysis of output characteristics performed, it may be noted:

- Sensitivity and nonlinearity are differed rather insignificantly in measurements when pressure is applied from the

topside or the backside. Average values of sensitivity and nonlinearity are $S = 34.5 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$ and $2K_{NL} = 0.81 \%FS$;

- Obtained errors $TCZ < 0.1 \%FS$ and $TCS < 0.3 \%FS$, compensated by an external signal processing circuit (ASIC), are sufficiently acceptable;
- THZ and THS increase at positive temperatures as compared with negative temperatures. General values of temperature hysteresis are relatively low for this ultralow pressure range and do not exceed $0.6 \%FS$ [46-48];
- Short-term time stability and signal variation due to the effect of mechanical overload are up to $0.3 \%FS$;
- A zero signal at turning the sensing element changes rather considerably, therefore the sensor can be used as accelerometer. On the other hand, this effect has a negative impact on its direct application as the crystal location and influence of the environmental vibration should be taken into consideration.

The selected structure of an assembly was analyzed with regard to free travel of the membrane of a chip of group No.2 up to the stops. As seen from Figure 8, the membrane travel remains free until the moment of touching $P_{touch \text{ samples}} = 2...5 \text{ kPa}$, when pressure is applied from either side of the chip. These chip samples of group No.2 were tested for structure destruction in the absence of stops in the assembly. The membrane is irretrievably deformed at $P_{burst \text{ without stops}} \approx 9 \text{ kPa}$ independently of the direction in which pressure is applied. When stops are used, the area of surface-to-surface contact between the membrane and stops is gradually reallocated at additional overload pressure and sensor is destroyed at a pressure above $P_{burst} = 450 \text{ kPa}$.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the developed mathematical model, the optimum geometry of a membrane structure has been defined and an ultrahigh sensitivity chip of a pressure sensor, operating in a ultralow differential pressure range of -0.5 to $+0.5 \text{ kPa}$ with $S = 34.5 \pm 4.1 \text{ mV/kPa/V}$ and $2K_{NL} = 0.81 \pm 0.50 \%FS$, has been realized. The difference in output characteristics measured when pressure is applied from the topside and the backside is relatively small (the difference in sensitivity is 2%) for the selected design of a chip. The samples show a certain spread in the rated values of sensitivity and sensor errors that can be minimized during further technological upgrading. The errors of temperature characteristics, time stability and overload ability of chips are also sufficiently small for the ultralow pressure range (Table 4). The RI inertial mass allows considering this chip as an ultrahigh sensitivity accelerometer. Additionally, an advantage has been achieved as the threshold of burst pressure P_{burst} was raised above 450 kPa owing to the use of stop elements in the assembly.

The presented structure of a pressure sensor may be valid for researches, involved in investigations in this field, from the viewpoint of further upgrade and fabrication of pressure sensors chips with ultrahigh sensitivity and low errors.

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of an ultrahigh sensitivity pressure sensor chip: a) topside, b) backside

Fig. 2. Map of MS distribution (a) and membrane deflection (b) for the selected membrane geometry at pressure 0.5 kPa

Fig. 3. Sensitivity (solid line) and nonlinearity (dot line) dependence on the pressure at variation of the membrane thickness W

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of an assembly comprising a chip, stops and a base

Fig. 5. Main process steps for an ultrahigh sensitivity pressure sensor chip (section A-A from Fig. 1)

Fig. 6. Examples of images of the obtained samples: a) rigid center geometry relative to PR regions, b) assembly in the package

Fig. 7. Variation of an output signal versus the applied pressure $\Delta V_{out}(\Delta P)$ for groups: a) No.2, b) No.1.1, c) No.1.2

Fig. 8. Variation of an output signal versus the pressure for several typical samples of ultrahigh sensitivity pressure sensors

TABLE I
MAIN GEOMETRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE SENSING ELEMENT

Geometrical Parameter	Size, μm
L	6150
Q_1/Q_2	1122/3366
W	8
H	420
A	4200
D	18
Z	400
Y	690
G	285

TABLE II

DIFFUSION PARAMETERS OF ULTRA-HIGH-SENSITIVITY PRESSURE SENSOR

Process step	Parameters
Oxidation	1100 °C, 15 min.-20 min.-15 min (dry-wet-dry)
Forming high-doped P ⁺ areas	Diffusion from unlimited source: 1050 °C, 55 min. Drive-in and oxidation: 1150 °C, 5 min – 15 min. – 5 min (dry-wet-dry)
Forming P ⁺ resistors	Ion implantation: D = 8.0·10 ¹⁴ cm ⁻² , E = 50 keV Impurity activation and oxidation: 1100 °C for 45 min in inert atmosphere followed by oxidation 1000 °C, 5 min – 35 min. – 5 min. (dry- wet-dry)
Forming N ⁺ areas	Diffusion from unlimited source: 1000 °C, 5+30+10 min. (Ar/O ₂ +Ar/O ₂ /POCl ₃ +Ar/O ₂) Drive-in and oxidation: 1000 °C, 5 min – 30 min. – 10 min (dry-wet-dry)

TABLE III

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL ERRORS

Parameters		Type of chip		
		№2	№1.1	№1.2
Sensitivity S, mV/V/kPa	Backside	34,2 ± 3,9	49,2 ± 8,6	73,2 ± 12,9
	Topside	34,8 ± 4,2	50,5 ± 8,9	75,2 ± 14,0
Nonlinearity 2K _{NL} , %FS	Backside	0,77 ± 0,48	3,5 ± 2,1	9,5 ± 2,9
	Topside	0,85 ± 0,52	4,5 ± 2,3	10,0 ± 3,2
ΔV ₀ (σ _r), mV		0,26 ± 0,26	1,61 ± 0,59	8,72 ± 6,22

TABLE IV

PERFORMANCE OF ULTRA-HIGH-SENSITIVITY PRESSURE SENSOR

Parameters	Value	
Sensitivity S, mV/V/kPa	Backside	34,2 ± 3,9
	Topside	34,8 ± 4,2
Nonlinearity 2K _{NL} , %FS	Backside	0,75 ± 0,48
	Topside	0,87 ± 0,52
Zero pressure output signal (Offset) V ₀ , mV/V	< 5	
TCZ (-30...+20 °C), %FS/°C	0,055 ± 0,051	
TCZ (+20...+60 °C), %FS/°C	0,048 ± 0,044	
TCS (-30...+20 °C), %FS/°C	0,280 ± 0,021	
TCS (+20...+60 °C), %FS/°C	0,234 ± 0,026	
Zero thermal hysteresis (THZ)		
(-30...+20°C), %FS	0,21 ± 0,13	
(+20...+60°C), %FS	0,34 ± 0,25	
Span thermal hysteresis (THS)		
(-30...+20°C), %FS	0,12 ± 0,11	
(+20...+60°C), %FS	0,21 ± 0,18	
Long-term instability		
of zero offset, %FS	0,18 ± 0,11	
of pressure sensitivity, %FS	0,10 ± 0,09	
Burst pressure P _{burst} , kPa	> 450	
Changing after proof pressure P _{proof}	zero, %FS	0,19 ± 0,11
	span, %FS	0,11 ± 0,08
Zero offset after turning on 180°, μV/V	52 ± 10	
Number of samples in statistics	62	